

Searching for a COVID-19 effect on wildfire activity in Portugal but not finding it: a comment on *Sci. Total Environ.* 765, 142793

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Keywords: Wildfire, Fire weather, COVID-19

Societal response to the COVID-19 pandemic implied diminished human mobility and activity. A decrease in the number of fires is expected to be the most direct impact of COVID-19, with possible further effects caused by pandemic-related restrictions to wildfire suppression preparedness and response. To assess the impact of such measures on wildfire activity, Rodrigues et al. (2021a) examined the anomaly in burned area at country level (Portugal, Spain, France, Italy, and Greece) in the March-May period of 2020 during which lockdowns and other restrictions were in place in those countries. The important influence of fire weather was controlled for by using a drought index, SPEI, the Standardized Precipitation Evapotranspiration Index, retrieved for the study period plus the preceding 3 months (December-February).

The SPEI has been used in a number of studies connecting fire activity to seasonal drought. However, drought indices are not expected to depict weather-related fire danger and fire activity as good as fuel dryness indexes specifically developed for such purpose, especially when the former are calculated for lengthy periods of time (Riley et al., 2013; Russo et al., 2017). Consequently, the SPEI should be seen as a supplement, rather than a proxy for fire danger rating (McEvoy et al., 2019). Additionally, the fuels governing fire-spread rate, thus individual fire size and overall burned area, are mostly the fast-drying finer fuel elements (Cruz et al., 2015). While a given fuel moisture threshold is required for fire to ignite and spread, fire behaviour will respond increasingly less to increasingly higher values of indexes for the moisture of slow-response fuels. For example, starting from a moisture content of ~250%, nearly all fine forest floor fuels in Mediterranean pine forests will be available to burn within one month in the absence of rain (Fernandes and Loureiro, 2013). Finally, wind speed is the primary engine of fire propagation, and more so in open vegetation such as shrubland, where fire spreads as a function of the atmospheric rather than the drought component of fire weather (Anderson et al., 2015). Additionally, fire activity displays regional to local synchrony, e.g. Jiménez-Ruano et al. (2019), but Rodrigues et al. (2021a) generalized the fire-weather analysis, i.e. burned areas per country were associated with the 6-months SPEI for the entire study area.

Rodrigues et al. (2021a) asserted that the “potential effects of weather on fire incidence” can be accounted for by using the SPEI alone; the statement was subsequently moderated in their reply (Rodrigues et al. 2021b) to Resco de Dios (2021). The authors concluded that spring 2020 burned-area in southern Europe was off by one order of magnitude given the level of observed seasonal drought, thus supporting a COVID-19 effect. As the potential shortcomings of the SPEI are manifest and Rodrigues et al. (2021a) assume their results as preliminary, further analysis is

warranted. Here, and for the specific case of Portugal, I explore to what extent fire activity relates with drought and atmospheric conditions, assessed from the unambiguous perspective of fire danger rating, and then inspect how the March-May period of 2020 compares with previous years. Then I examine whether the number of fires in 2020 diminished, using 2018-2019 as the baseline and controlling for confounding effects; a longer time series would be misleading, since the number of fires in Portugal has been steadily decreasing since the early 2000s (Rego et al. 2020).

The Portuguese wildfire information management system allows associating each fire record (defined by a measurable area burned) with the daily fire weather indexes calculated from the nearest weather station data. Portugal, like many other countries, adopted the Canadian Forest Fire Weather Index (FWI) System for fire danger rating. Within the FWI System, the Initial Spread Index (ISI) and the Buildup Index (BUI) respectively describe the atmospheric and the drought (or fuel availability) components of fire weather. Thus the ISI accounts for the influences of fine dead fuel moisture content and wind speed, and the BUI is an outcome of rainfall, temperature, and relative humidity. Summing the annual (2003-2020) number of fires and area burned for the months of March to May, as in Rodrigues et al. (2021a), and regressing those metrics on the corresponding mean ISI and BUI values enables assessing the relative influence on fire activity of the two fire weather components (Fig. 1). The superiority of the ISI in explaining variation (about half of it) in fire activity in comparison with the BUI is manifest. Interestingly, Fig. 1 points to 2020 as the year with both the least fire activity and the mildest fire weather since 2003, differently from Rodrigues et al. (2021a) findings and obfuscating the detection of a COVID-19 effect.

Fig. 1. Number of fires and burned area in mainland Portugal as a function of the atmospheric (Initial Spread Index) and drought (Buildup Index) components of the Canadian Forest Fire Weather Index (FWI) System, for the March-May periods of 2003 to 2020 (red dot). The fitted curves are of the form $y = a \exp(bx)$.

I fitted a generalized linear model to 2018-2019 data assuming a Poisson distribution and a log link function to describe daily fire counts in Portugal ($n=629$). The model explains 56% of the variation and includes the following independent variables, sequenced by decreasing order of importance and all significant at $p < 0.0001$: the ISI; month, to account for seasonal variation in human-caused fire patterns, e.g. use of fire for land management; year, to account for the ongoing temporal trend of decreased number of ignitions; and the BUI. The model was used to estimate the daily number of fires in 2020 from the 1st of January to the 30th of September 30. Then the predictions were summed for each of four 2020 periods, defined by the severity of governmental measures as per INSA (2020), respectively Pre-COVID-19 (weeks 1-12), Emergency (weeks 13-18), Post-Emergency (19-38), and Contingency (39-40). Deviations in the number of recorded fires relative to the number of predicted fires are given in Table 1, where the deviation is the difference between the observed and the predicted number, divided by the number predicted and then expressed as a percentage. Deviation from the expected number of fires indicates a near half decrease during the most stringent phase (Emergency, from late March to the beginning of May), suggesting an effect of COVID-19 related measures. However, the previous period (prior to any governmental measures) experienced a slightly higher decrease. While the hypothesis of a pandemic-related decrease in number of ignitions cannot be excluded, the results are more likely to reflect reinforcement of stricter policies and greater compliance by people in the aftermath of the catastrophic fire events of 2017. Still, the number of fires during the Post-Emergency phase increased 83% above model expectation. This phase was the mildest regarding COVID-19 control and includes the summer months, hence presumably higher incidence of intentionally-caused fires that are less likely to be affected by fire prevention measures. Additionally, one can speculate that the unusually mild fire weather of March-May (Fig. 1) may have moved pastoral burning into the summer months.

Table 1. Number of fires predicted by the model developed with 2018-2019 data and observed in Portugal from the 1st of January to the 30th of September 2020 and by COVID-19 phase. Strength of the governmental measures follows the gradient Emergency > Contingency > Post-Emergency.

Phase	Predicted	Observed	Deviation (%)
Pre-COVID-19	843	385	-54.3
Emergency	450	236	-47.6
Post-Emergency	4268	7806	82.9
Contingency	177	174	-1.7

Models for the annual burned area in Portugal indicate that the relative influence of weather- and fuel-related variables exceeds the influence of the number of fires (≥ 1 ha) by a factor of 2.5 (Fernandes et al., 2019). Note that these fires are just 20% of the total fire count and that a decrease in the number of fires does not decrease burned area in the same proportion, as a very small fraction of the total number of fires accounts for most of the burned area. It is reasonable to consider, like Rodrigues et al. (2021b), that humans are more decisive to burned area in winter-spring than in summer. Still, the top-down control should not be overlooked: while the use of fire in the frame of rural land management is widespread in regions such as northern Portugal and NW Spain, fire weather alone will decide whether it will be materialized into fire activity. Regardless of variation in the seasonal role of people in starting and terminating a fire, whether or not an ignition will actually spread and attain a significant size is conditional on the spatiotemporal context for the ignition, as determined by fire weather and the landscape. This further complicates attempts at attributing changes in fire activity in relation to human behaviour in response to COVID-19. To conclude, analysis of fire-weather relationships and fire activity, even if preliminary, should consider the mechanisms at play as thoroughly as possible. Adequate understanding of cause-effect relationships will not be achieved otherwise, as shown here for fire activity in Portugal in March-May 2020.

Acknowledgments

The author contributed to this article in the framework of the UIDB/04033/2020 project, funded by the Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT).

Competing interests: I confirm that there are no known potential competing interests.

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